

Republic of the Philippines
Department of Education
Ramon Magsaysay (Cubao) High School
Address: Ermin Garcia St, corner EDSA,
Brgy. Pinagkaisahan, Quezon City
Tel No: (02) 637 6754

**Potential Degrading Capability of White Oyster Mushroom
(*Pleurotus ostreatus*) to Conventionally
Used Polyethylene Plastics**

A Science Investigatory Project
made in Partial Fulfillment
of the Requirements in
Research 2

MARC ANDRIE M. BERMUNDO
RYAN LOUIE B. MEDINA
FRANCIS EMMANUEL A. CALARAMO
Proponents

MS. AMYLENE Y. CATAYAS
Research Adviser

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Potential Degrading Capability of White Oyster Mushroom (*Pleurotus ostreatus* Jacquin ex. Fr.) to Conventionally Used Polyethylene Plastics

¹Bermundo, Marc Andrie M., ¹Calaramo, Francis Emmanuel A., ¹Medina, Ryan Louie B., & ²Ms. Amylene Y. Catayas

¹Students, ²Teacher, Ramon Magsaysay (Cubao) High School

ABSTRACT

Plastics become a common problem in waste management due to the fact that it takes hundreds or thousands of years to disintegrate into the environment. A step for bioremediation for plastics is using saprophytic fungi like the genus *Pleurotus*. The study explores the possibility that fungi of the said genus have the possibility to degrade the content of polyethylene. In this study, the researchers implanted the polyethylene films as a substrate in growth mediums with different soil and spawn content so the fungi will propagate on top of the plastic while degrading it. Observation was done within four weeks. Results show that the yield of the mushrooms is lower than cultivated mushrooms but the segment of the films have their densities depleted in four weeks' time via electronic single pan balance test. This paper concludes that using mushrooms as plastic decomposers will be effective in degrading rubbish with the purpose of crumbling without problems and a few suggestions for the degradation of plastics using fungi. The importance of the present study is the potential use of mushrooms as a natural decomposer for polyethylene plastics-in particular. Applications of these results can be proposed if the mushrooms are used to degrade the many plastics in landfills within a short period of time.

Keywords: *Biodegradation, Pleurotus ostreatus, Mycoremediation, LDPE, HDPE*

INTRODUCTION

The creation of synthetic polymer products is one of the greatest breakthroughs of humanity in the present times. The flexible use of plastics such as packaging and manufacturing of different products, the many types of plastics has become more utilizable and long-lasting as the times go by. Such plastics can be used as an alternative material for natural products, for the reason that some products take time before consumption or they are rare to find and produce something out of it. Living in this time has become easier due to the convenient usage of plastics.

Out of this, humanity didn't realize the toll of using plastics as an essential tool for mankind. And now, there is no plausible solution for getting rid of waste plastic except for reusing it again into other material. Nowadays, plastics became a big problem in the whole world. Many types of plastics take hundreds or thousands of years before disintegrating into the environment. The occurrence of plastics that will never be absorbed into the earth again such as polystyrene, commonly known as Styrofoam, is also a major threat in the world as it pollutes the land and water. Numerous studies have been done to introduce ways to diminish the amounts of plastic waste that destroy the environment as they last for a long period of time. Some studies do show a promising way for removing plastics, but they do not give a pure way to deduct the number of plastics in the world. The situation worsens as time passes by, since a couple of studies show that microplastics are now found in human stools.

The Philippines is one of the biggest contributors of plastic waste in the world, as it releases 2.7 million tons of waste per year, according to a news report by The Philippine Star in 2018. In conjunction with this, dumpsite accidents in our country are common because there is no proper disposal system in our country and these areas are not mandated properly by the authorities. Problems with plastics cause substantial ranges of pollution in urban areas, especially in our country, which suffers from the garbage brought by major bodies of water like the Manila Bay, Marikina River, and Pasig River along with its tributaries, some of which are considered to be as "dead" bodies of water which also cause flooding in some parts of the region.

The rigorous spending of plastics is the major reason why it is the principal pollutant of all garbage that people contribute on a daily basis. Another major problem about plastics is the obscure nature that it possesses. Reducing the content of wastes brought by plastic materials is the main goal of this research. The path of this study that it will take is to test if the oyster mushroom can be able to degrade various plastics in a matter of weeks or months, this could be of great convenience for many especially those countries that are now heavily polluted.

This led to the researchers in studying if some species of fungi have the possibility to degrade common types of plastic such as polyethylene. In this study, the researchers will be using *Pleurotus ostreatus*, which are generally identified as the white oyster mushroom that are cultivated globally, especially in Southeast Asia, India, Europe and Africa. The study limits itself to the capabilities of the used mushroom, as the *Pleurotus* genus may have discrepancies in biodegradation according to previous studies, although they are saprophytic in nature and can break through polymers easily. The mushrooms also need to be taken care of to ensure the successfulness of the study, along with the proper soil concentrations, substrate, and water for faster rates of proliferating and degrading.

REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

Fungi are comprised of eukaryotic organisms such as molds, yeast, and mushrooms. As heterotrophic fungi, they secrete digestive enzymes in their environment in order to live. Their movement is based on their growth wherein they multiply in numbers.

There are numerous quantities of studies that pertain to the capabilities of fungi as bioremediators. Various environmental functions of the fungi species in nature are the foundations of ecological fidelity in the forest. Fungi are an essential component of forest ecosystems and a significant constituent for their subsistence and refurbishment. Greater notice in recent times remunerated to their involvement in silviculture, woodland fortification, and the regaining the quality of the forest. Pavlík studied that *Pleurotus*

species are naturally found on decaying wood or growing timber. Recent studies show that the People's Republic of China produces 64% of all edible mushrooms in the world and 85% of all oyster mushrooms all over the world.

Farming of mushrooms is the fifth largest agricultural division in China with a value of \$24 billion and has a rising rate of improvement in the last 30 years by ten percent. The mounting expenditure and interest of oyster mushroom is escalating fundamentally due to its savor, medicinal and dietary properties. *Pleurotus* spp. is commercially cultured all over the year by using sawdust and/or rice straw as main substrates, said by Tesfaw *et. al.* But the productions of these mushrooms are not economically beneficial in every season.

Here in the Philippines, we already got the relative humidity of 70-80% and the regular conditioning of 14-27°C, which is good for the growing parameters of oyster mushrooms. *Pleurotus* spp. grows in an extensive range of temperature (15-30°C) which also varies from the species. Bano and Rajarathnam observed maximum yield of oyster mushroom (*P. sajor-caju*) during rainy seasons, when the temperature was nearly 20-26°C and relative humidity 70-90%. Maximum growth of *P. ostreatus* was recorded at 25°C by Rangad and Jandaik. Kong reported that *P. ostreatus*, *P. florida* & *P. sajor-caju* reach their most advantageous growth at 25°C.

The species also happens to decay oxo-biodegradable plastic, as stated in the paper of da Luz *et. al.* and may weaken other polyethylene plastic types and has a future to be a natural decomposer for plastic polymers.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Gathering Mushroom Spawns

Commercially-sold spawns of *Pleurotus ostreatus* were bought by the researchers at Koko's Mushroom located at #62 Kalapati Street, Novaville Subdivision, Novaliches, Quezon City. Six packaged bottles of mushroom spores were brought for the study.

Figures 3.1.1 – 3.1.2 – The commercially-sold spawns of *Pleurotus ostreatus* at Koko's Mushroom at Novaliches, Quezon City.

Formulation of Fruiting Bag Setups

Fruiting bags were made from different polyethylene terephthalate (PET) bottle setups. Each setup is a pair of bottles with different spawn amount. Three PET bottles, cut in in the middlemost section, will act as the fruiting bags in this study. that are labeled with "1" will hold low-density polyethylene (LDPE) plastics, and the remaining three will be marked as "2" and contain high-density polyethylene (HDPE) plastics. The numbers of the bottles dictate the number of spawns into them. Setups marked with "A" have 25% spawn amount, "B" with 50% spawn amount, and "C" with 75% spawn amount.

The setups were then sent to the school's biology laboratory in Ramon Magsaysay (Cubao) High School for setting up the said formulation bags.

Figures 3.1.3 – 3.14 – The formulation of the fruiting bag set-up. A plastic sheet to be used is inserted as an example on where it will be placed during the course of the

Preparation of Plastics into the Fruiting Bags

The low-density (LDPE) and high-density (HDPE) polyethylene plastic sheets were prepared and they were inserted into the setups as a part of the substrate. The fruiting bag setups were distinguished after the type of polyethylene plastic sheets that will be inserted in them. Only the spawn amount is differentiated for this study. The plastic sheets were boiled first before the substrate at 80°C.

Figures 3.1.5 – 3.1.6 – The low-density polyethylene (LDPE) plastic sheets (above) and the boiling of the substrate (below).

Proliferation of Mushrooms

Substrates were pasteurized for about 25 minutes in 80°C. Then they are left with the desired temperature in order to grow in their desired condition. Different layers were made for the set-up containers. The bottom layer is the soil and above are the plastic sheets and on the peak are the substrates and spawns mixed together. The setups were placed in dark areas with low temperature and high moisture.

The fruiting bag setups have pores on the bottom part in order to let excess hydration flow and for the fungi to propagate. Setups are watered up to 65%, which is equivalent to 490 mL on a 1.5 L bottle on a daily basis to keep the spawns humid.

Figures 3.1.7 – 3.1.8 – The fruiting bag set-up of a PET bottle with 25% spawn amount inserted with low-density polyethylene (LDPE) plastic sheets.

Decomposition of Plastic Sheets via Proliferation

The activity of the fungi and the plastics are observed for four weeks. The fungi are watered on a daily basis. After the last week, the plastics were dragged away from the fruiting bag setups and will look after the plastic sheets carefully so they will proceed on the measurements.

Figures 3.1.9 – 3.1.10 – A fruiting bag set-up of a PET bottle with 50% spawn amount inserted with high-density polyethylene (HDPE) plastic sheets after four weeks (above) and the same plastic sheets recovered after four weeks (below).

Biological Yield of Mushrooms While Exposed On Plastic

The developmental prospective can be determined by the yield of growth that happens onto it. It will test the competence of our mushrooms while it is exposed to a growing medium with plastics. The yield can be deliberated by the following formula below:

$$\text{Biological Yield of Oyster Mushroom} = \frac{\text{Weight of Dry Mushroom (Harvested)}}{\text{Weight of Dry Substrate (Before Insertion)}} \times 100\%$$

Figures 3.1.11 – 3.1.12 – Preparation for the biological yield of the mushrooms after four weeks of being exposed to polyethylene plastic sheets.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Measuring Growth Yields

Using the formula for the biological efficiency for the growth of mushrooms, the yields are listed in the table below. It is implied that different dry weights of the used substrates do affect the growth yield of the mushrooms, causing the other setups to grow better than the other apparatuses that the researchers used in the present work. The yields are lower than the yields using natural substrates because natural substrates have less time to disintegrate.

Table 1: Yields of Fruiting Bag Setups after Four Weeks

Time	Growth Yield					
Number of Weeks	A (25% Spawn Amount)		B (50% Spawn Amount)		C (75% Spawn Amount)	
1	7.89% (LDPE)	7.93% (HDPE)	7.78% (LDPE)	7.81% (HDPE)	8.60% (LDPE)	8.02% (HDPE)
2	10.53% (LDPE)	10.73% (HDPE)	10.36% (LDPE)	10.47% (HDPE)	11.45% (LDPE)	10.72% (HDPE)
3	15.78% (LDPE)	15.63% (HDPE)	15.45% (LDPE)	15.62% (HDPE)	17.22% (LDPE)	16.04% (HDPE)
4	31.54% (LDPE)	35.53% (HDPE)	31.11% (LDPE)	31.23% (HDPE)	34.34% (LDPE)	32.07% (HDPE)

Here, the researchers formulated this table to show the yield of the growing mushrooms after two weeks, in the paired bottles, only setups 1B (LDPE with 50% spawn amount), 2A (HDPE with 25% spawn amount), and 2B (HDPE with 50% spawn amount) belong to the upper bound on the growth rate and the other setups belong to the lower bound of the growing rate of the oyster mushrooms. The yields are calculated after the fourth week, which is the time period that we are observing the mushrooms. Table 1 shows the whole table of the yield of the setups and the referenced figures below shows the respective bar graph of what is represented out in the table.

Weakening of Plastic Sheets by Determining the Change in Density

In this study, the researchers evaluated the values that they've gotten for the assessment. The researchers have done the practical way, which is to look at the difference in densities. The difference in densities will also denote that other plastic properties are decreased or affected since the density of LDPEs and HDPEs already affects their creep condition and toughness. The researchers used water with the exact measure of 30°C as immersion liquid in order to devise the electronic single pan balance method. The formula for the density of the plastics is shown below:

$$\text{Density} = \frac{\text{Weight of Dry Mushroom (Harvested)}}{\text{Volume of Water}} \times (0.9962) \text{ g/cm}^3$$

Table 2: End results in the actual density of LDPE and HDPE plastics in a period of four weeks by *Pleurotus ostreatus*

Time (in weeks)	Actual Density (g /cm³)	
	HDPE	LDPE
1	3.15	3.35
2	2.68	2.98
3	2.13	2.22
4	1.43	1.32

Figure for Table 2: End results in Actual Density of Inserted Plastics in a period of four weeks.

The graph shows the time lapse of the decrease of the actual density of the setups of LDPE & HDPE after hauling the plastics from the mushroom fruiting bags. Actual density, which is represented in g/cm^3 , has a slow start during the observation period but it showed a significant amount of decrease during the next three weeks.

CONCLUSION

The researchers discovered a significant amount of material change in the polyethylene film; slight fluctuations in its arrangement, density and other recognized factors from when it was not yet rotten. It suggests that white oyster mushrooms were doing well in decomposing the polyethylene film. Findings in this study are alike to that of the papers of da Luz et. al. in their mycological research in degrading oxo-biodegradable

plastic. Observations revealed that the mushrooms also grow at a normal rate, not as anticipated in a slower pace and there was a weakening of the composition of the plastic, this helps in a rapid and quick method in evaluating plastics, in particular low-density polyethylene (LDPE) and high-density polyethylene (HDPE) types.

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RECOMMENDATIONS

The researchers would like to recommend that there might be possible circumstances regarding the incomplete dissoluteness of the plastic type, the given results in this recent study may be used as a referential tool for future research regarding plastic degradation.

PHOTO CREDITS

The photos present in this paper are owned by Marc Andrie M. Bermundo, Francis Emmanuel A. Calaramo, and Ryan Louie B. Medina. All of the photographs seen in this article was taken during the course of their study.

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APPENDICES

APPENDIX A: TABLES AND GRAPHS

Table 1: Yields of Fruiting Bag Setups after Four Weeks

Time	Growth Yield					
Number of Weeks	A (25% Spawn Amount)		B (50% Spawn Amount)		C (75% Spawn Amount)	
1	7.89%	7.93%	7.78%	7.81%	8.60%	8.02%
	(LDPE)	(HDPE)	(LDPE)	(HDPE)	(LDPE)	(HDPE)
2	10.53%	10.73%	10.36%	10.47%	11.45%	10.72%
	(LDPE)	(HDPE)	(LDPE)	(HDPE)	(LDPE)	(HDPE)
3	15.78%	15.63%	15.45%	15.62%	17.22%	16.04%
	(LDPE)	(HDPE)	(LDPE)	(HDPE)	(LDPE)	(HDPE)
4	31.54%	35.53%	31.11%	31.23%	34.34%	32.07%
	(LDPE)	(HDPE)	(LDPE)	(HDPE)	(LDPE)	(HDPE)

Table 2: End results in the actual density of LDPE and HDPE plastics in a period of four weeks by *Pleurotus ostreatus*

Time (in weeks)	Actual Density (g /cm ³)	
	HDPE	LDPE
1	3.15	3.35
2	2.68	2.98
3	2.13	2.22
4	1.43	1.32

Figures for Table 1: Yields of LDPE & HDPE Setups after Four Weeks in Fruiting Bag Set-ups.

Figure for Table 2: End results in Actual Density of Inserted Plastics in a period of four weeks.

APPENDIX B: VERIFICATION OF USED SPECIMEN (*P. ostreatus*)

(to be seen on the next page)

Koko's Mushroom Oysterlicious

Address: #62 Kalapati Street, Novaville
Subdivision, Novaliches, Quezon City

This is to certify that the bottled mushroom spawns bought by Mr. Marc Bermundo, Mr. Francis Calaramo, and Mr. Ryan Medina are of the species of **white oyster mushroom (*Pleurotus ostreatus Jacquin ex. Fr.*)** that they will be using for their **research study**.

QUANTITY BOUGHT: FOUR (4) BOTTLES OF WHITE OYSTER MUSHROOM SPAWNS

A handwritten signature in black ink that reads 'Eliza Rebadulla'. The signature is written in a cursive, flowing style.

Eliza Rebadulla

Owner, Koko's Mushroom